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INVESTIGATION OF THE KINETIC MODEL OF THE PROCESS OF DEHYDROGENATION OF ETHYLBENZENE INTO STYRENE

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Annotation: The article is devoted to the study of the kinetics of the ethylbenzene dehydrogenation process in a two-stage adiabatic reactor.

The analysis of chemical reactions occurring in parallel with the main reaction of styrene formation was carried out, on the basis of which a number of assumptions were made, on the basis of which a kinetic scheme was compiled that describes the mechanism of chemical transformations during the dehydrogenation process. A kinetic model of the process has been developed. The dependences of the change in the concentration of the starting substance were obtained. The adequacy of the mathematical model of the process was checked.

Keywords: dehydrogenation of ethylbenzene, adiabatic reactor, chemical kinetics, a mathematical model, reaction rate constant

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ КИНЕТИЧЕСКОЙ МОДЕЛЬ ПРОЦЕССА ДЕГИДРИРОВАНИЯ ЭТИЛБЕНЗОЛА В СТИРОЛ

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Аннотация: Статья посвящена исследованию кинетики процесса дегидрирования этилбензола в двухступенчатом адиабатическом реакторе.

Проведен анализ химических реакций, протекающих параллельно основной реакции образования стирола, исходя из чего сделан ряд предположений, на базе которых составлена кинетическая схема, описывающая механизм протекания химических превращений во время процесса дегидрирования. Разработана кинетическая модель процесса. Получены зависимости изменения концентрации исходного вещества. Проверена адекватность математической модели процесса.

Ключевые слова: дегидрирование этилбензола, адиабатический реактор, химическая кинетика, математическая модель, константа скорости реакции

Styrene is one of the most important petrochemical products and raw materials for the production of polymer materials. Currently, the main industrial method of styrene production in Russia is the catalytic dehydrogenation of ethylbenzene. The main stage of the process under consideration is the separation of the hydrogen molecule from the ethylbenzene charge entering the reactor, since it is at this stage that the final product, styrene, is formed. Therefore, today the task of intensifying this production stage is relevant on the basis of optimizing the operating mode of the process using mathematical modeling methods. In conditions of limited raw materials, financial, time and Ph.D. production resources, methods of mathematical modeling and optimization are the most promising. Since this does not require the cost of technical implementation and makes it possible to make this process less resource- and energy-intensive, as well as to increase the percentage of styrene produced in the reaction mixture at the reactor outlet. The ethylbenzene dehydrogenation reaction process is carried out in an adiabatic two-stage continuous reactor (with a catalytic zone along the length of each stage) at a temperature of 560oC at the initial stage of operation of the catalytic system with an increase in this value to 630 oC by the end of its service life. Basically, dehydrogenation is carried out on iron oxide catalysts, the time cycle of which is 2 years, after which they are subject to replacement [1-3]. Based on the above, a kinetic scheme of the process was obtained describing the mechanism of the reaction of styrene formation and reactions of the release of by-products

of dehydrogenation, in the creation of which the following assumptions were made: 1) as a result of the interaction of the formed styrene molecules with hydrogen molecules, toluene and carbon are released (benzene and ethylene are not formed); 2) reaction products such as benzene and ethylene are formed only as a result of the decomposition reaction of ethylbenzene. 3) the rate constants of the formation of monomolecular components, as well as direct and reverse reactions are not equal; 4) the values of the constants of the formation rates of the components of bimolecular reactions occurring during dehydrogenation are the same for each reaction. As a result (according to the accepted assumptions), the kinetic scheme of dehydrogenation will take the form [4-6]:

Reaction of styrene and hydrogen formation:

Reaction of benzene and ethylene formation:

Toluene and methane formation reaction:

Reaction of carbon and hydrogen formation:

Reaction of formation of carbon dioxide and hydrogen:

Reaction of carbon monoxide and hydrogen formation:

The reaction of the formation of toluene and carbon as a result of the interaction of styrene molecules with hydrogen molecules:

When developing a mathematical model of the process, the following assumptions are made: 1) The temperature regime of the reactor is considered constant and is equal to 560 °C. 2) The change in the activity of the catalytic system during the process is not taken into account. 3) The values of the rate constants of all reactions are considered constant (a consequence of assumption 1). Thus, using the compiled kinetic scheme, we obtain a mathematical description of the styrene production process for each stage of the reactor unit. The mathematical model is a system of

differential equations describing the dynamics of changes in the concentrations of ethylbenzene and reaction products during the course of the process:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dCa}{dt} &= k_1 C_b - \frac{k_3}{kp} C_a C_c \\ \frac{dCb}{dt} &= \frac{k_3}{kp} C_a C_c - k_1 C_b - k_2 C_b - k_4 C_b - k_5 C_b \\ \frac{dCc}{dt} &= k_2 C_b + k_7 C_g - k_{10} C_h C_p^2 \\ \frac{dCd}{dt} &= k_4 C_p \\ \frac{dCe}{dt} &= k_5 C_b \\ \frac{dCf}{dt} &= k_6 C_b C_c \\ \frac{dCg}{dt} &= \frac{k_{13}}{kp} C_m C_c - k_7 C_g \\ \frac{dCh}{dt} &= k_7 C_g - k_9 C_h C_p^2 \\ C_a(0) &= 0, C_b(0) = 0.998, C_c(0) = C_d(0) = 0.001, C_e(0) = C_f(0) = C_g(0) = 0, \\ C_h(0) &= C_k(0) = C_m(0) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

where t is the time of passage of the charge layer through the reactor block stage c ; $C_a, C_b, C_c, C_d, C_e, C_f, C_g, C_h$ are the concentrations of styrene, ethylbenzene, toluene, benzene, carbon, hydrogen, methane, ethylene, respectively, by mass fraction; k_1, k_4, k_5, k_7 – the rate constants of the formation of styrene, benzene, ethylene and carbon, respectively, c^{-1} ; (k_3 / k_p) – the rate constant of the reverse reaction of the formation of styrene, c^{-1} / mass fraction; k_6 – the rate constant of the formation of toluene and methane, c^{-1} / mass fractions; k_2, k_p is the equilibrium constant, c^{-1} . The values of the kinetic parameters of the model, which are the rate constants of the reactions occurring, except k_p , are unknown. The equilibrium constant is calculated for a specific value of the reaction temperature according to the following dependence [7]:

$$k_p = 16.72 \cdot \exp(-15.35/T),$$

where T is the temperature in the dehydrogenation reactor, °K., $T = 833K$, $k_p = 16.429 c^{-1}$. The constants were estimated using a numerical optimization method of the search type of coordinate descent [8], according to the criterion of the minimum of the average total relative error of component concentrations after each stage of the reactor unit: The parameters k_1, \dots, k_7 found as a result of identification are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 – Values of the rate constants of monomolecular reactions

Name	Constant value speed, c^{-1}
K_1	0.367
K_2	0.0022
K_3	0.003
K_4	0.00213
K_5	11.431
K_6	0.385
K_7	0.323

The calculation of the system of equations of the mathematical model was performed for each of the two reactor stages using the Runge-Kutta numerical method of the 4th order. The final concentrations of ethylbenzene dehydrogenation products obtained as a result of the calculation of the first stage of the reactor are the initial data for modeling the process in the second stage. The results of modeling the process of dehydrogenation of the ethylbenzene charge layer during its passage through the catalytic zones of the stages are shown in Tables 2, 3.

Table 2 – The composition of the reaction mixture at the outlet of the first stage of the reactor

The concentration of the main reaction products, % wt.		Concentration of reaction by-products, % wt		Total concentration of components, % wt.
Styrene	31.623	Toluene	0.436	2.929
Ethylbenzolazole	62.631	Benzene	2.493	
		Ethylene	1.388	1.587
		Carbon	0.199	
		Methane	$4.1 \cdot 10^{-3}$	
		Hydrogen	1.155	1.235
		Carbon monoxide	0.012	
		Carbon dioxide	0.064	

Table 3 – The composition of the reaction mixture at the outlet of the second stage of the reactor

The concentration of the main reaction products, % wt.		Concentration of reaction by-products, % wt		Total concentration of components, % wt.
Styrene	50.444	Toluene	1.672	5.666
Ethylbenzolazole	39.308	Benzene	3.996	
		Ethylene	2.259	2.873
		Carbon	0.614	
		Methane	$5.3 \cdot 10^{-3}$	
		Hydrogen	1.039	1.715
		Carbon monoxide	0.038	
		Carbon dioxide	0.613	

According to the received data on the model: 1) at the exit from the first stage of the reactor, the concentrations of reaction products are in the following ranges: – styrene concentration 30-35 %; – the concentration of ethylbenzene is 60-65 %; – the total concentration of toluene and benzene should not exceed 5 %; – the total concentration of gases (H_2 , CH_4 , CO , CO_2) is not more than 1.5 %. 2) at the exit from the reactor unit (from the second stage of the reactor), the concentrations of reaction products are in the following ranges: – styrene concentration 50-55 %; – concentration of ethylbenzene 35-40 %; – the total concentration of toluene and benzene should not exceed 8 %; – the total concentration of gases (H_2 , CH_4 , CO , CO_2) is not more than 2 %.

The analysis of the simulation results showed the quantitative and qualitative compliance of the calculated values with the data given in the technological regulations. This indicates the adequacy of the developed model of the chemical kinetics of ethylbenzene dehydrogenation, as well as the validity of the estimates of the rate constants of the chemical reactions of the process. The developed mathematical description can be used to create a system for optimal control of the dehydrogenation stage in the styrene production process.

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